

1 Title:

2 A new chromosome-assigned Mongolian gerbil genome allows characterization of complete
3 centromeres and a fully heterochromatic chromosome

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27 **Abstract**

28 Chromosome-scale genome assemblies based on ultra-long read sequencing technologies are
29 able to illuminate previously intractable aspects of genome biology such as fine-scale
30 centromere structure and large-scale variation in genome features such as heterochromatin, GC
31 content, recombination rate, and gene content. We present here a new chromosome-scale
32 genome of the Mongolian gerbil (*Meriones unguiculatus*) which includes the complete sequence
33 of all centromeres. Gerbils are thus the second vertebrate, after humans, to have their
34 centromeres completely sequenced. Gerbil centromeres are composed of four different repeats
35 of length 6pb, 37bp, 127bp, or 1747bp which occur in simple alternating arrays and span 1-6Mb.
36 Gerbil genomes have both an extensive set of GC-rich genes and chromosomes strikingly
37 enriched for constitutive heterochromatin. We sought to determine if there was a link between
38 these two phenomena and found that the two heterochromatic chromosomes of the Mongolian
39 gerbil have distinct underpinnings: Chromosome 5 has a large block of intra-arm
40 heterochromatin as the result of a massive expansion of centromeric repeats, while
41 chromosome 13 is comprised of extremely large (>150kb) repeated sequences. In addition to
42 characterizing centromeres, our results demonstrate the importance of including karyotypic
43 features such as chromosome number and the locations of centromeres in the interpretation of
44 genome sequence data, and highlight novel patterns involved in the evolution of chromosomes.

45 **Introduction**

46 Understanding the organization and function of genomes and how they vary has been
47 an important goal in the field of biology since at least the 1950s. The new and relatively
48 inexpensive long-range sequencing technologies such as PacBio HiFi and Oxford Nanopore are
49 facilitating the sequencing and chromosome-scale assembly of the genomes of many new
50 species (Jayakumar and Sakakibara 2017). Such high-quality genomes are an important tool to
51 address long-standing questions about variation in the structure and function of genomes
52 across the tree of life. Such questions include: What is the nucleotide sequence and structure of
53 centromeres in non-model species? What is the recombination landscape and how does it
54 influence nucleotide content variation in genes and along chromosomes? In addition and often
55 overlooked: what new insights can be gleaned when we reinterpret cytological data, such as the
56 banding patterns of chromosomes in a karyotype, in light of chromosome-scale assemblies?

57
58 Centromeres are crucially important during mitosis and meiosis. Functionally, they are
59 the binding site of centromere-specific histones and other proteins which facilitate their binding

60 to the spindle apparatus (McKinley and Cheeseman 2016). They are visible in karyotypes as
61 constrictions in the chromosome which stain very darkly under different chemical treatments
62 (Willard 1990). They are characterized by arrays of various repeated sequences of DNA of
63 various lengths, where the sequence of the repeat is species-specific (Talbert and Henikoff
64 2020). Due to their size and repetitive nature, they have proven intractable to assembly by all
65 but the most recent of long-range sequencing technologies, indeed it is only within the last year
66 that human centromeres have been completely sequenced and annotated (Altemose et al.
67 2022). An immense amount of work has gone into studying centromeres at the functional level
68 using visualization techniques, but very little is known about the specific sequence of
69 centromeres in most species. Sequencing and characterizing centromeres in various non-model
70 species is and will be an important addition to understanding the variation and function of
71 centromeres across the tree of life.

72

73 The nucleotide composition of genomes is not homogenous; it varies along chromosome
74 arms and between chromosomes, individuals, populations, and species (Eyre-Walker and Hurst
75 2001). Variation in the distribution of guanine (G) and cytosine (C) bases is heavily determined
76 by the recombination-associated process of GC-biased gene conversion (gBGC), which favours
77 fixation of guanine and cytosine over adenine (A) and thymine (T)(Lamb 1984; Arbeithuber et al.
78 2015). Over evolutionary time this process results in a GC bias around recombination hotspots
79 (Galtier et al. 2001). Gerbils and their relatives have multiple extensive regions of extremely
80 high GC bias within their genomes, higher than that seen in any other mammal (Hargreaves et
81 al. 2017; Dai et al. 2020; Pracana et al. 2020). Historically, this has complicated attempts to
82 obtain high-quality contiguous gerbil genome assemblies (Leibowitz et al. 2001; Gustavsen et
83 al. 2008). Intriguingly, there appear to be two distinct patterns of GC skew in gerbils: (i) a region
84 associated with the ParaHox cluster and the surrounding genes, where virtually all genes in this
85 region have very high mutation rates and an extreme GC bias, and (ii) a further set of 17 large
86 clusters of GC-rich genes also with high mutation rates (Pracana et al. 2020). These intriguing
87 characteristics of gerbil genomes make them an ideal system in which to examine the
88 association between GC biased gene conversion and the organization of eukaryotic genomes.

89

90 Chromatin state is an important mechanism for the regulation of gene activity.
91 Facultative heterochromatin is cell-type-specific and may be converted to open, active
92 euchromatin during gene regulatory processes. In contrast, constitutive heterochromatin is
93 marked by tri-methylation of histone H3 at the lysine 9 residue (H3K9me3) (Saksouk et al. 2015)

94 and comprises densely compacted, gene-poor inactive regions of the genome which are
95 condensed in all cell types at all developmental stages, such as centromeres and telomeres
96 (Saksouk et al. 2015; Penagos-Puig and Furlan-Magaril 2020). Many gerbil species (Family
97 Gerbillidae) have chromosomes with high levels of constitutive heterochromatin, though the
98 specific chromosome and extent of heterochromatin vary by species. Mongolian gerbils possess
99 distinctive karyotypic features (Figure S1): nearly a third of Chromosome 5 and all of
100 Chromosome 13 appear to be composed of constitutive heterochromatin by multiple different
101 assays: Chromosome 13 stains entirely dark in C-banding stains (Gamperl and Vistorin 1980)
102 and is completely coated by heterochromatin histone marks in immunofluorescence assays (de
103 la Fuente et al. 2014).(Gamperl and Vistorin 1980) The genomes of the North African Gerbil
104 (*Gerbillus campestris*), the hairy-footed gerbil (*Gerbilliscus pæba*), and the fat sandrat
105 (*Psammomys obesus*) all contain a single heterochromatic chromosome (Solari and Ashley
106 1977; Gamperl and Vistorin 1980; Knight et al. 2013).

107 The heterochromatic chromosomes in gerbils are present in all individuals examined to
108 date and do not meet the criteria for classification as B chromosomes, i.e.: they are not non-
109 essential, and do not vary in copy number among individuals and tissues without an adverse
110 impact on fitness (Ahmad and Martins 2019). These chromosomes therefore provide a unique
111 system to examine the impact of their heterochromatic state on genic evolution and particularly
112 whether it is linked to the extensive number of GC-rich genes in gerbil genomes.

113 Heterochromatin is typically gene-poor (Dimitri et al. 2005) and transcriptionally repressed
114 (Grewal and Moazed 2003; Dillon 2004). This makes it unlikely that entire heterochromatic
115 chromosomes would be maintained and transmitted across generations for millions of years if
116 they did not encode any genes or are entirely selfish independent genetic elements. High GC%
117 in certain gerbil genes could be an adaptation to a transcriptionally-repressive environment.
118 Genes with high GC% in their coding regions and adjacent regions of DNA, and especially
119 those with high GC% in the 3rd codon position (GC₃) can show elevated expression (Lercher et
120 al. 2002; Vinogradov 2005). Conversely, since gBGC is a recombination-dependent process,
121 and since all chromosomes must undergo at least one reciprocal recombination event
122 (crossover) with their homologue during meiosis (Lydall et al. 1996), an alternative hypothesis is
123 that the extreme GC% present in some gerbil genes is a consequence their becoming
124 entrapped in or near a recombination hotspot. If the bulk of the extensive heterochromatin
125 observed on these gerbil chromosomes is non-permissive to recombination, then genes in those
126 regions where recombination can occur will become increasingly GC-rich because of continual

127 exposure to gBGC. We may therefore reasonably expect a link between GC-rich genes and
128 these unusual gerbil chromosomes.

129 A key question is how did fully heterochromatic chromosomes in gerbils arise? They may
130 once have been “normal” chromosomes that have degenerated into gene-poor, non-functional,
131 or silenced chromosomes by accumulation of repetitive DNA. Alternatively, they may have
132 formed from heterochromatic pieces that broke off from other chromosomes, in the same way
133 that the neochromosomes of tumors (Garsed et al. 2009, 2014) and some B chromosomes
134 (Camacho et al. 2000; Dhar et al. 2002) develop from fragments of other chromosomes.
135 Alternatively they could be the duplicate of another chromosome, which condensed into
136 heterochromatin a mechanism of dosage compensation in the same way that additional copies
137 of X chromosomes are inactivated in female mammals (Lyon 1962). Finally, they may potentially
138 have grown from a smaller chromosomal “seed”, which broke off from another chromosome,
139 and subsequently grew by repeated segmental duplication.

140 Until very recently, questions such as those posed above could not be addressed in a
141 non-model system for several key reasons. A particularly important issue was the difficulties that
142 short read-based genome sequencing approaches face regarding the assembly of GC%-rich
143 regions (Hron et al. 2015; Bornelöv et al. 2017; Botero-Castro et al. 2017; Tilak et al. 2018; Yin
144 et al. 2019). Meanwhile, the current trend towards the generation of chromosome-scale
145 assemblies has perhaps lost sight of the importance of an understanding of the karyotype of the
146 species being studied, and of physically linking genome sequence to identified chromosomes.

147 Using a new chromosome-scale genome assembly for the Mongolian gerbil and
148 methods enabling us to assign the genomic scaffolds to physical chromosomes, we first
149 characterize gerbil centromeres and then test (i) whether GC-rich gene clusters correlate with
150 recombination hotspots and (ii) if those genes are associated with a single heterochromatic
151 chromosome. Our approach allows us to examine the origin and propose a new hypothesis for
152 the evolution of some unusual and possibly unique, heterochromatic gerbil chromosomes.

153

154 **Results and Discussion**

155 Gerbil genome: approach and summary statistics

156 We sequenced and assembled the genome of the Mongolian gerbil, *Meriones*
157 *unguiculatus*, into 245 contigs using PacBio HiFi reads (2,699,742,000 total bases, $N_{50} =$
158 58,726,396, $L_{50} = 16$, $N_{90} = 15,971,047$, $L_{90} = 48$). We scaffolded the contigs with OmniC

159 chromatin conformation capture data (Figure S2), Oxford Nanopore long and ultra-long read
160 sequence data, a genetic map (Table S1) (Brekke et al. 2019), and BioNano optical mapping.
161 We assigned scaffolds to chromosomes by flow-sorting chromosomes into pools. Each pool
162 was sequenced with Illumina short reads, and these reads used to determine which scaffolds
163 associated with each pool. The sorted pools were also made into FISH paint probes to identify
164 which physical chromosome from the karyotype associated with each pool. This approach
165 linked the physical chromosomes with sequenced scaffolds (full methods are in Supplemental
166 Material 1, Figures S1, S3-S7, and Tables S2 and S3). The final genome assembly contains
167 194 scaffolds spanning 21 autosomes, the X and Y sex chromosomes, and the mitochondrial
168 genome (Table S4). For 20 of the 23 chromosomes, a single large scaffold contains over 94%
169 (often over 99%) of all the sequence assigned to that chromosome (Figure 1A). Only
170 chromosome 13, with 121 scaffolds, and the X and Y chromosomes, each with 6 scaffolds, are
171 appreciably fragmented and there are only 30 unassigned scaffolds making up 0.066% of the
172 sequenced bases (Figure 1B). The assembly was annotated using RNAseq data and is 92%
173 complete based on a BUSCO analysis (Complete:92.3% [Single-copy:91.7%, Duplicated:0.6%],
174 Fragmented:1.7%, Missing:6.0%, n:13798) (Manni et al. 2021). We used the program NeSSie
175 (Berselli et al. 2018) to calculate two measures of sequence complexity (entropy and linguistic
176 complexity) in sliding windows across every chromosome. The complexity metrics revealed two
177 chromosomes with unusual features: Chromosome 5 which has an extensive region where both
178 entropy and linguistic complexity are very low, and Chromosome 13 which shows a marked
179 homogeneity in its entropy across the length of the chromosome (Figure 2 and Figure S8). A
180 chromosome-by-chromosome summary of all data is found in Figure 3 and a high-resolution
181 version is in Supplement 2.

182 Two *M. unguiculatus* genome sequences have been previously published, based on
183 short-read sequence data (Cheng et al. 2019; Zorio et al. 2019), both contain hundreds of
184 thousands of contigs and equally large numbers of scaffolds (Table S4). One of these has
185 recently been improved with Hi-C data (www.DNAZoo.org) into 22 chromosome-length
186 scaffolds, and ~300,000 additional scaffolds (Cheng et al. 2019). Full-genome alignments
187 between our genome assembly and this Hi-C assembly (Figure S9) showed that most scaffolds
188 are colinear between the assemblies but that the “improved” Cheng et al. (Cheng et al. 2019)
189 assembly lacks chromosome 13 entirely, hence only 22 chromosome-scale scaffolds for this
190 species with 23 unique chromosomes (21 autosomes, an X and a Y; Figure S1). Our highly
191 contiguous and physically associated assembly provides the foundation for all subsequent
192 analyses.

193

194 Characterization of gerbil centromeres

195 Relatively little is known about centromere organization in non-model species, as
196 centromeres are comprised of extensive runs of repeated sequences, which short-read
197 technologies (and even Sanger sequencing) have struggled to cross. It is only this year that full
198 coverage of human centromeres was obtained, from a mixture of long-read sequencing
199 approaches applied to the genome of a hydatidiform mole cell line by the Telomere-to-Telomere
200 (T2T) consortium (Altemose et al. 2022). Our high-quality PacBio HiFi-derived sequence data
201 resulted in a single large scaffold per chromosome (for all but a few chromosomes) which
202 spanned from telomere to telomere (Figure 1). Such completeness suggested that we
203 sequenced through the centromeres of all *M. unguiculatus* chromosomes and so we set about
204 bioinformatically identifying centromeres. Centromeres are known to be highly repetitive, occur
205 once on each chromosome, are visually apparent as a constriction in the karyotype, and are
206 typically on the order of a few megabases long (Talbert and Henikoff 2020). We used the
207 entropy and linguistic complexity metrics (measures of sequence repetitiveness) to reveal a
208 region of each chromosome that matched the above predictions: every chromosome has a
209 single highly repetitive region ranging from ~1-10Mbp long which line up with the constriction in
210 the karyotype (Figure 2 and Figure 3). As we did no molecular assay for centromere function,
211 we submit these as “putative centromeres”, though for brevity, we hereafter refer to them simply
212 as “centromeres”.

213 To further characterize the gerbil centromeres, we used the program NTRprism
214 (Altemose et al. 2022) which identified four different simple repeat sequences (Figure S10). We
215 have named these “MsatA” (for *Meriones satellite A*), “MsatB”, “MsatC”, and “MsatD” (Figure
216 3A): MsatA is 6bp long and has the sequence TTAGGG which is the same simple sequence
217 repeat found in telomeres, MsatB is 37bp long, MsatC is 127bp long, and MsatD is 1,747bp long
218 and is only found on the Y chromosome. A representative sequence of each Msat can be found
219 in the legend of Figure S10. At the time of writing, MsatB and MsatC return no BLAST hits from
220 NCBI’s ‘nt’ library (update 2023/01/12) and MsatD returns a single 32bp run of identity (out of
221 1748bp) with *Acomys russatus* suggesting that these Msats are new sequences not previously
222 identified.

223 Copies of Msats are arranged into one of four variant arrays which define an
224 intermediate-order structure in the centromeres (Figure 3B). ‘B arrays’ are formed from copies

225 of MsatB and range in size from 1Mbp to 3Mbp long (~30,000 to ~100,000 copies). Similarly,
226 the Y chromosome centromere is a 'D array' comprised of ~500 copies of MsatD spanning
227 slightly less than a megabase. MsatA and MsatC repeats are rarely found alone, tending
228 instead to intersperse with each other to form 'A-C arrays'. Typically 10-50 copies of MsatA will
229 alternate with 5-10 copies of an MsatC unit, and this alternating pattern will extend for between
230 100Kb and 1Mb depending on the chromosome. The only place that MsatC are found without
231 interspersed copies of MsatA is on the X chromosome in what we term a 'C array'. While not
232 interspersed with MsatC, there are a number of MsatA repeats that do appear at both ends of
233 the X centromere and are detectable by FISH (de la Fuente et al. 2014). The orientation of the
234 Msat repeats is typically consistent across an array, however some arrays are composed of
235 blocks of Msat repeats in alternating orientations with many copies of repeat in the forward
236 orientation followed by many copies in the reverse orientation.

237 The highest-level of centromere organization is characterized by groups of between one
238 and three arrays which fall into one of a few patterns which we term 'simple', 'asymmetric', or
239 'symmetric' (Figure 3C). Simple centromeres are comprised of a single A-C array and are
240 present in ten of the smaller metacentric chromosomes (see chromosomes 3, 5, 6, 8-12, 15,
241 and 16, Figure 3D). The metacentric Y chromosome also has a simple centromere, though with
242 a D array instead of the A-C array. Asymmetric centromeres are comprised of two arrays, one of
243 which is always a B array and the other is typically an A-C array. Eight autosomes fall into this
244 category including all four of the small telocentric chromosomes (Chromosomes 18-21, Figure
245 3D), three of the metacentric chromosomes (Chromosomes 4, 7, and 14, Figure 3D), and one
246 acrocentric chromosome (Chromosome 17, Figure 3D). The metacentric X chromosome also
247 has an asymmetric centromere but is the only location in the genome where a pure C array
248 exists. Finally, symmetric centromeres are comprised of three arrays: a C array sandwiched
249 between two A-C arrays and are found in the metacentric chromosomes 1, and 2, and the
250 acrocentric chromosome 13. Many centromeres also contain 10Kbp–50Kbp blocks of non-
251 repetitive, complex DNA both between and within the various arrays (see Figure 3D).

252

253 The location of GC-rich genes

254 A set of over 380 genes with extreme GC content clustered in the genomes of sandrats
255 and gerbils has previously been identified (Pracana et al 2020). It has been hypothesized that
256 biased gene conversion has driven their GC content to extraordinary levels since they are near

257 recombination hotspots (Pracana et al. 2020), but the resources to test this were not available
258 so mouse gene locations had been used as an evolutionarily-informed proxy for the location of
259 those genes in gerbils. Here we use our newly-generated chromosome-scale assembly to
260 explicitly test how these GC-rich genes are distributed across gerbil chromosomes. We used a
261 permutation test to show that GC-rich genes are clustered together more than is expected by
262 chance (Figure 4A, observed = 1.71Mbp, mean = 2.89Mbp, n=1,000,000 permutations, $p <$
263 0.000001). We used our genetic map (Brekke et al. 2019) to locate recombination hotspots
264 which were defined as regions with 5x higher recombination rate than the genome average (as
265 per (Katzer et al. 2011). Hotspots were found on 18 of 22 chromosomes (21 autosomes and the
266 X chromosome, we omit the Y chromosome here as it does not recombine) with 2.4 ± 2.2 (sd)
267 hotspots per chromosome (Figures S11, S12, S13). Chromosomes 2, 18, 21, and the X lack
268 recombination hotspots. We tested proximity of GC-rich genes to hotspots in two ways, first by
269 comparing the GC-rich genes with the entire gene set (Figure S14) and secondly by performing
270 a permutation test (Figure 4B). In both cases, GC outlier genes were found to lie significantly
271 closer to recombination hotspots than expected by chance (Figure 4B, observed = 21.68Mbp,
272 mean = 27.29Mbp, n = 1,000,000, $p <$ 0.00058). These results demonstrate a clear association
273 of GC rich gene clusters with recombination hotspots as expected under gBGC.

274 While a genetic map shows the location of current recombination hotspots, hotspots
275 move through evolutionary time due to large-scale chromosomal rearrangements and the
276 mutational load caused by crossing over (Paigen and Petkov 2010; Tiemann-Boege et al.
277 2017). Consequently, we next tested whether GC outliers are associated with proxies of
278 ancestral hotspots. Recombination rate is not uniform across a chromosome and is typically
279 higher near the telomeres (Nachman 2002; Martinez-Perez and Colaiácovo 2009), thus we
280 tested whether GC outliers are correlated with position along the chromosome arm. We found
281 that whether considering the full distribution of gene locations (Figure S15) or 1,000,000 draws
282 of the same number of random genes in a permutation test (Figure 4C), the GC outliers are
283 found to lie much closer to the telomere than expected by chance (Figure 4C, observed =
284 71.46%, mean = 49.78%, n=1,000,000, $p <$ 0.000001). Furthermore, gerbils have many
285 interstitial telomere sites (de la Fuente et al. 2014) which are caused by chromosomal fusions
286 embedding what was an ancestral telomere within a chromosome arm, typically near the
287 centromere. Thus, interstitial telomere repeats are proxies for the ends of ancestral
288 chromosomes and their associated ancient recombination hotspots. We identified interstitial
289 telomere sites as arrays of the 6bp “MsatA” with at least 70 tandem copies (Figure S16). We
290 therefore tested whether GC outlier genes are closer to these telomere repeats (which could be

291 interstitial or otherwise) than expected by chance and found that they are (Figure 4D, observed
292 = 11.79Mbp, mean = 15.06Mbp, n=1,000,000, p < 0.000001; Figure S17). In short, GC outlier
293 genes are found in clusters across the genome and are nearer to recombination hotspots
294 (current or ancient) and telomere/interstitial telomere sites than expected by chance, strongly
295 supporting the hypothesis that GC-biased gene conversion is driving the extreme GC content of
296 these genes. Figure S18 shows the distribution of centromeres, recombination hotspots, high
297 GC genes, and telomere sites that were used in these analyses.

298 However, we did not find that all GC-rich genes are located on heterochromatic
299 chromosomes and find instead that they are distributed on the order of 19.5 ± 13.7 GC-rich
300 genes per chromosome across the genome. The tendency for genes to become highly GC-rich
301 in and around recombination hotspots in gerbils therefore seems unrelated to their unusual
302 chromosomes and may instead be the result of greater recombination hotspot stability, where
303 hotspots stay in one place for longer in gerbils compared to other species. Similarly stable
304 hotspot location has previously been reported for birds (Singhal et al. 2015) though in birds the
305 absence of PRDM9 correlates with greater hotspot stability. The gerbil genome encodes a full-
306 length *Prdm9* gene on chromosome 20, and so this hotspot stability in gerbils must arise via
307 some other mechanism.

308 We next sought to understand the genomic basis of the heterochromatic appearance of
309 the chromosomes 5 and 13 in *M. unguiculatus*.

310

311 *Chromosome 5: the relevance of centromeric drive*

312 Chromosome 5 is characterized by an enormous centromeric repeat expansion which is
313 visible as a dark band on the q arm (Figure 3D). Our data shows that the repeat expansion is a
314 29Mb long B array, which comprises approximately 22% of the entire chromosome. This repeat
315 expansion is distinct from the centromere which is a simple A-C array 1.5Mb long. In contrast to
316 the B arrays in the centromeres of other chromosomes, the orientation of MsatB repeats on
317 chromosome 5 switches far more frequently. With a few exceptions, B arrays in centromeres
318 maintain their orientation across the entire array, or in the case of the symmetric centromeres,
319 have a few large blocks in opposite orientations; the centromeric B arrays maintain orientation
320 for 1-3Mb. Repeats in the Chromosome 5 expansion however, switch orientation over 200 times
321 across the 29Mb, so the average block length is just 140Kb.

322 There is a similar large expansion of a centromeric repeat found in human chromosome
323 9 (Altemose et al. 2022). However, while it is similar in size to the expansion on gerbil
324 chromosome 5, the human expansion is polymorphic in the population (Craig-Holmes and Shaw
325 1971). The dark band on the q arm of gerbil chromosome 5 is visible in all published karyotypes
326 dating back to the 1960s which derive from many different individuals and laboratory colonies
327 (Pakes 1969; Weiss et al. 1970; Gamperl and Vistorin 1980) suggesting that in contrast, the
328 gerbil expansion is fixed at this massive size.

329 The repeat expansion is absent in karyotypes of many closely related Gerbillinae
330 species, including representatives from the genera *Desmodilus*, *Gerbillurus*, *Gerbillus*, *Tatera*,
331 and *Taterillus*, and is even absent in other species of *Meriones*. (Gamperl and Vistorin 1980;
332 Benazzou et al. 1982, 1984; Qumsiyeh 1986b,a; Dobigny et al. 2002; Aniskin et al. 2006;
333 Volobouev et al. 2007; Gauthier et al. 2010). The expansion is also absent in the sequenced
334 genome assemblies of the closely related fat sandrat (*Psammomys obesus*) and fat-tailed gerbil
335 (*Pachyuromys duprasi*). Alignment with the *Psammomys* genome assembly shows that the
336 location of the repeat expansion on *M. unguiculatus* chromosome 5 is homologous to the
337 *Psammomys* chromosome 10 centromere (Figure S19), suggesting that the region in *M.*
338 *unguiculatus* is an ancestral centromere that has expanded. The centromere-drive hypothesis
339 (Malik 2009) may explain the distribution of array types in the autosomal centromeres under the
340 following model: the ancestral gerbil centromeres were predominately B arrays and at some
341 point after the *Meriones* – *Psammomys* split, centromeric drive triggered a massive repeat
342 expansion of the B array on what would become *Meriones* chromosome 5. This runaway
343 expansion was the catalyst for genome-wide centromere turnover, where A-C arrays replaced B
344 arrays as the new functional centromeres and many B arrays were evolutionarily lost, with those
345 that remained being non-functional relics. Indeed, the centromere expansion on chromosome 5
346 does not bind CENT proteins, although it preserves other heterochromatic marks, (such as
347 H3K9me3) and excludes recombination events, as assessed in male meiosis by the localization
348 of the recombination marker MLH1 (Figure 5). While the heterochromatic state of a large portion
349 of chromosome 5 can therefore be explained by the massive expansion of a centromeric repeat,
350 this is not the case for chromosome 13.

351

352 *Chromosome 13: origin of a new autosome*

353 Chromosome 13 is the most unusual chromosome in the gerbil genome for a variety of
354 reasons. Karyotypically, it stains very dark and appears heterochromatic in G (Figure 3D) and
355 C-banding images (Gamperl et al. 1977; Gamperl and Vistorin 1980). It also displays delayed
356 synapsis during the first meiotic prophase, when compared to all other chromosomes (de la
357 Fuente et al. 2007, 2014). On a technical level, it is the only chromosome that failed to
358 assemble into a single chromosome-length scaffold (Figure 1), and even optical mapping was
359 unable to improve the assembly. In a phylogenetic context there is no ortholog of chromosome
360 13 in mouse and rat, but similarity in G-banding patterns suggests that it may share ancestry
361 with chromosome 14 in the fat sandrat (*P. obesus*). Short reads assigned to chromosome 13
362 have very low mapping quality as they map to multiple locations. As a result, chromosome 13
363 has very few genetic markers and a very short relative genetic map length compared to the
364 other chromosomes (Table S1) and we suspect this is what prevented the OmniC data and
365 HiRise pipeline from successfully assembling this chromosome. The centromere of
366 chromosome 13 is unique in that the A-C arrays have more non-repetitive blocks interspersed
367 within them than the other chromosomes (Figure 3D), and in terms of sequence complexity,
368 there is no fine-scale variation in entropy across the chromosome (Figure 3, Figure S8) as on
369 the other autosomes, suggesting very low sequence diversity. Indeed, the entropy of
370 chromosome 13 appears even more homogenous than that of the Y chromosome (Figure 3,
371 Figure S8). Chromosome 13 has more than the expected number of genes based on its size
372 (Figure 6A), but far fewer unique genes (Figure 6B), demonstrating high levels of gene
373 duplication: of the 1,990 genes on chromosome 13 annotated as something other than “Protein
374 of unknown function”, 566 are copies of a viral *pol* protein (and so represent either endogenous
375 retrovirus or LET retrotransposon sequences), 406 are *Vmn2r* (olfactory receptor) genes (of
376 which 337 are copies of *Vmn2r116*) and 331 are *Znf* (Zinc finger) genes (257 of which are
377 *Znf431*). There are more GC-rich genes located on chromosome 13 than expected based on its
378 size (Figure 6C) and Chromosome 13 houses the original high-GC cluster (including the
379 *ParaHox* genes) identified by (Hargreaves et al. 2017; Pracana et al. 2020). Chromosome 13
380 has a far higher repetitive sequence content (Figure 6D), as measured by the EarlGrey pipeline
381 (Baril et al. 2022) which is clearly visible in comparison with other chromosomes in a self-
382 alignment plot (Figure 5E-M). In fact, after filtering out alignments under 1,000bp, over 93% of
383 bases on chromosome 13 are found in multiple copies on the chromosome, compared with
384 ~10% on other autosomes (e.g. 11.5%, 8.2%, and 12.7% on the similarly sized chromosomes
385 10, 11, and 12 respectively). The bulk of chromosome 13 consists of around 400 copies of a

386 block of DNA 170kb long, the periodicity and variable orientation of which can easily be seen in
387 Figures 5H, 5I, and 5J. While we find no evidence of a link between high GC% genes and this
388 chromosome generally, chromosome 13 does encode the set of genes previously identified as
389 being the most extreme outliers in gerbil and sandrat genomes (Pracana et al. 2020). These
390 genes surrounding the ParaHox gene cluster include *Pdx1*, *Cdx2*, *Brca2* and others crucial for
391 proper embryogenesis and cell function (Withers et al. 1998). The cluster is contained within an
392 ancient genomic regulatory block (Kikuta et al. 2007), where genes are locked together by the
393 presence of overlapping regulatory elements. The presence of the most unusual genes on the
394 most unusual chromosome is very interesting and is consistent with a model where the selective
395 pressure to keep this block of genes intact may have had a role in the formation of the
396 chromosome.

397 We propose the following model to explain the origin of chromosome 13: a chromosomal
398 fragment approximately 5 million bases long which included the ParaHox cluster (Hargreaves et
399 al. 2017) broke off from an ancestral chromosome, perhaps during a genome rearrangement.
400 The ParaHox genes and many of their neighbours are crucially important during development
401 and so could not be lost altogether. For example: *Pdx1*^{-/-} mice die shortly after birth (Jonsson et
402 al. 1994; Offield et al. 1996) as do those lacking *Brca2* (Evers and Jonkers 2006) *Insr* (Accili et
403 al. 1996) or *Hmgb1* (Calogero et al. 1999) function; *Cdx2*^{-/-} mice die within the first 5 or 6 days
404 of development (Chawengsaksophak et al. 1997); 75% of *Gsx1*^{-/-} mice die within 4 weeks of
405 birth, and none live beyond 18 weeks (Li et al. 1996); and *Flt1*^{-/-} mice die *in utero* (Fong et al.
406 1995). These are just a small selection of genes in this region, but they demonstrate the
407 selective pressure(s) that must exist for its maintenance within the genome. While the simplest
408 option might have been for this fragment to have joined onto or into another chromosome, this
409 does not appear to have happened, and instead we propose that this chromosomal fragment
410 became the seed for the growth of an entirely new chromosome. In some species, the
411 evolutionary fate of such a fragment may be long-term persistence as a microchromosome: a
412 small, gene-dense, repeat-poor, GC-rich chromosome of ≤ 30 Mb with a high recombination rate.
413 But while microchromosomes are common in birds, reptiles, and fish, they do not persist in
414 mammals over evolutionarily time (Srikulnath et al. 2021; Waters et al. 2021). Efficient
415 transmission of mammalian chromosomes between generations and into daughter cells
416 therefore seems to require a minimum size, and in the case of *M. unguiculatus* chromosome 13,
417 we propose the hypothesis in which the fragment grew rapidly via a breakage-fusion-bridge
418 mechanism, (McClintock 1938, 1941; Bignell et al. 2007; Campbell et al. 2010; Greenman et al.
419 2012), where the chromatid ends without a telomere fuse, and then are pulled apart at

420 anaphase, breaking randomly and resulting in long inverted repeats. The patterns apparent in
421 the Chromosome 13 self-alignments (Figure 6G, 6H, 6I) are consistent with what would be
422 expected under this model and may explain how a 170kb region at the end of the chromosome
423 was repeatedly duplicated, at multiple scales, until a 107Mb chromosome was formed. The high
424 similarity of these duplicated regions explains our difficulty in assembling this chromosome, the
425 multimapping of short reads, and the failure of BioNano optical mapping to improve our
426 assembly.

427 While the repetitive nature of Chromosome 13 is consistent with it arising and evolving
428 under the model described above, that does not explain why Chromosome 13 houses genes
429 with the most extreme GC content. Previous authors (Gamperl and Vistorin 1980) have
430 described that chromosome 13 forms ring-like structures during meiosis, suggesting that the
431 bulk of the heterochromatic material on this chromosome does not, or possibly cannot, form
432 chiasma, and therefore cannot undergo recombination. However, based on localization of the
433 recombination marker MLH1, we have found evidence of recombination during male meiosis
434 (Figure 5). Bivalent chromosome 13 presents a recombination event in most spermatocytes,
435 although a small proportion (around 23%) lack MLH1 foci. Strikingly, MLH1 are not evenly
436 distributed along this chromosome, as previously reported for other chromosomes (de la Fuente
437 et al. 2014). Instead, recombination events are strongly concentrated at the chromosome ends.
438 We therefore propose that the extreme GC skew of the ParaHox-associated genes in gerbils is
439 the result of the inability of recombination hotspots to move out of this genomic region, leading
440 to runaway GC-bias.

441 Conclusion

442 The two heterochromatin-rich chromosomes of Mongolian gerbils have distinct origins.
443 Chromosome 5 has undergone a massive expansion of a centromeric repeat, most likely as a
444 result of meiotic drive, and Chromosome 13 has likely arisen *de novo* from an initially small
445 seed via multiple breakage-fusion-bridge cycles. In general, these results show the importance
446 of karyotypic knowledge of study species and serve as a warning for large-scale genome
447 sequencing programs such as the Vertebrate Genomes Project (VGP) or the Darwin Tree of
448 Life Project (DToL) that we must not neglect knowledge of chromosome number and
449 morphology. Had we not known the diploid chromosome number for *M. unguiculatus*, and had
450 we not performed chromosome sorting and FISH, we likely would have binned the 121
451 fragments corresponding to chromosome 13 into the “unknown” category and may have even
452 deduced that gerbils had one fewer chromosome than they actually have. We applied what are

453 becoming the standard approaches for genome sequencing and assembly to the *M.*
454 *unguiculatus* genome (PacBio HiFi, chromatin conformation capture, Oxford Nanopore long
455 reads, and Bionano optical mapping), and incorporated chromosome sorting, FISH, and a SNP-
456 based linkage map, and were still unable to assemble chromosome 13 into a single scaffold.
457 The huge size and high similarity of the chromosome 13 repeats suggest that only ultra-long
458 Oxford Nanopore reads, on the order of several hundred kilobases, might be able to achieve the
459 telomere-to-telomere coverage of this enigmatic chromosome.

460

461 **Materials and Methods**

462 The complete details of the methods are available at the end of Supplemental Material 1, here
463 follows a very brief overview.

464 For sequencing and assembly, we extracted DNA from gerbil liver and sequenced to a
465 depth of 34X using PacBio HiFi technology. Genome assembly was done with the program
466 HiFiAsm (Cheng et al. 2020). Scaffolding was done using a combination of Dovetail OmniC,
467 Oxford Nanopore Ultra-long sequencing, Bioano Optical Mapping and a genetic map from
468 (Brekke et al. 2019). The genome was annotated using RNAseq from kidney and testis from
469 three individuals. Repeats were annotated using the EarlGrey pipeline (Baril et al. 2022).

470 For cell culture, chromosome sorting, and FISH we cultured cells from the gerbil fibroma
471 cell line IMR-33 and extracted chromosomes for cell sorting after being arrested in mitosis.
472 Chromosome sorting was done with a BD Influx Cell sorter into the 17 pools containing one or
473 two chromosomes. Each pool was sequenced with Illumina MiSeq. FISH paints were made from
474 each pool as well.

475 For mitotic chromosome preparation and FISH we cultured fresh spleen cells which were
476 then arrested in mitosis for chromosome spreads. These were stained with DAPI and the FISH
477 probes derived from the chromosome sorting and visualized on a confocal microscope.

478 For meiotic chromosome preparation and immunofluorescence, we extracted meiotic
479 cells from fresh testis and processed them for spreads and immunofluorescence. Slides were
480 incubated with the primary antibodies goat anti-SYCP3 to mark the synaptonemal complex,
481 rabbit anti-histone H3 trimethylated at lysine 9 to mark heterchromatin, human anti-centromere,
482 and mouse anti-MLH1 to mark meiotic crossovers. Then slides were incubated with secondary

483 antibodies and visualized with an Olympus BX61 microscope equipped with appropriate
484 fluorescent filters and an Olympus DP72 digital camera.

485 We assigned the sequenced scaffolds with the chromosomes in the karyotype by aligning
486 the reads from the sequenced pools to the scaffolds and identifying which pools' reads most
487 often aligned to each scaffold. Then we linked the pools to the karyotype by staining mitotic
488 chromosome spreads with the FISH probes derived from each pool.

489 We calculated GC content and gene density for each chromosome in sliding windows of
490 size 1kb and 1Mb respectively with step size 1kb. We calculated recombination rate with a
491 sliding window of 8 markers with a step of 1 marker and regressed marker position against
492 physical position. Hotspots were identified as a region whose recombination rate was 5x the
493 genome average. Entropy and Linguistic complexity were calculated with the program NeSSie
494 (Berselli et al. 2018) using a sliding window of size 10kb with a step of 1kb.

495 Centromeres were located at the trough of the linguistic complexity plot and the fine-
496 scale structure was analysed with NTRprism (Altemose et al. 2022) and TandemRepeatFinder
497 (Benson 1999). Interstitial telomeres were identified as those with >70 copies of the telomere
498 sequence in the TandemRepeatfinder data. Self-alignments were done with mummer (Kurtz et
499 al. 2004).

500

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512

513 **Authors contributions**

514 O.F. and E.J.– chromosome sorting, editing manuscript
 515 F.Y. and B.F. – FISH, editing manuscript
 516 T.B. and A.H. – EarlGrey, repeat annotations, editing manuscript
 517 J.P and R. d. I. F. – recombination/histone analyses, editing manuscript
 518 T.D.B., J. F. M., and A. S. T. P. – conceived study, genome sequencing, assembly, analysis,
 519 overall coordination, writing and editing manuscript

520

521 **Competing interests**

522 The authors declare no competing interests.

523

524 **Data and materials availability**

525 All sequencing data and the genome is available under SRA BioProject PRJNA397533.
 526 Specific accession numbers can be found in Supplemental Material 1.

527

528 **Tables and Figures**

529

530 Figure 1: Summary statistics for the Mongolian gerbil (*Meriones unguiculatus*) genome
 531 assembly. Top: The number of scaffolds assigned to each chromosome, the mitochondrial

532 genome, and the 'unknown' category. Most chromosomes are assembled into 1 or 2 scaffolds,
533 while chromosome 13 is in 121 pieces. Bottom: The number of bases assigned to each
534 chromosome with the single longest scaffold shaded in grey. The total amount of DNA
535 sequence assigned to chromosome 13 is about what would be expected, showing that we are
536 not missing data, and that the large number of scaffolds is not an artefact.

537

538

539 Figure 2: Entropy plots for a selection of chromosomes including the morphologically standard
540 autosomes 1 and 21, the unusual autosomes 5 and 13, and both sex chromosomes. The
541 unordered scaffolds within a chromosome are shaded alternately white and grey. Centromeres
542 are apparent at ~75-80Mbp in Chr1, ~0-5Mbp in Chr21, ~35-40Mbp in Chr5, ~14-17Mbp in
543 Chr13, ~45-50Mbp in ChrX, and ~75Mbp in ChrY. Note the spatial heterogeneity in
544 chromosomes 1 and 21 that is absent in chromosome 13 and the Y. Indeed, chromosome 13 is
545 the most homogenous chromosome in the gerbil. Entropy plots for every chromosome, as well
546 as GC content, gene density, and linguistic complexity can be found in Figure S2.

547

548

549 Figure 3: The Mongolian gerbil (*Meriones unguiculatus*) genome. Gerbil centromere types. (A)
 550 There are four different repeat types in gerbil centromeres: MsatA (6bp), MsatB (37bp), MsatC
 551 (127bp), and MsatD (1,747 bp). (B) These repeats appear in one of four repeat arrays. The A-C
 552 array consists of 10-50 copies of MsatA alternating with 5-10 copies of MsatC, all of which is
 553 repeated 150-1,500 times. The B-, C-, and D- arrays contain only multiple copies of their

554 respective repeat. Repeat units within an array most often occur in the same orientation. In
555 some chromosomes however both orientations occur within a single array, in which case
556 hundreds of repeat units in the forward orientation are followed by hundreds of units in the
557 reverse orientation (e.g. the B array of Chromosome 2 in Figure 2). (C) Centromeres consist of
558 between one and three repeat arrays and are classed as either 'simple', 'asymmetric', or
559 'symmetric'. Simple centromeres have a single array type, either an A-C array as in the
560 autosomes, or a D array as on the Y Chromosome. Asymmetric centromeres have two arrays:
561 either an A-C array and a B array (for the autosomes) or a C array and a B array (for the X
562 chromosome). Symmetric centromeres consist of three arrays, a B array sandwiched between
563 two A-C arrays which typically appear in opposite orientation to each other. (D) Genome
564 schematic, for each chromosome we show, from left to right: (1) centromere organization, with
565 repeats of different lengths in different colors and the orientation of the repeat array denoted by
566 a grey or black bar on the left. Chromosome 5 has a large expansion of centromeric repeats in
567 the long arm. All call-outs are drawn to the same scale. (2) The DAPI-banding karyotype image,
568 showing the intra-arm heterochromatin on chromosome 5, and the entirely dark staining on
569 chromosome 13. (3) Linguistic complexity and (4) entropy, both measured in overlapping sliding
570 10kb windows with a step size of 1kb. For both metrics, a low value indicates highly repetitive or
571 predictable sequence as are characteristic of centromeres while high values indicate more
572 complex sequence as may be found in gene-rich regions. (5) A depiction of the physical map
573 with unplaced scaffolds organized by length and shaded alternately white and grey, and (6) a
574 depiction of the genetic map with links between the genetic markers and their physical location.
575 Thin grey lines link the location of similar features on adjacent plots (i.e. centromere callout to
576 karyotype; centromere location in the karyotype to centromere in the linguistic complexity plot;
577 genetic markers to their physical location). A high-resolution copy of panel D can be found in
578 the Supplemental Material 2.

579

580

581 Figure 4: GC-rich genes are nonrandomly distributed in the *M. unguiculatus* genome. We
 582 compared the location of the 410 GC rich genes (Pracana et al. 2020) in relation to each other,
 583 the nearest recombination hotspot, their location along the chromosome arm, and their proximity
 584 to telomere repeats both interstitial and at the ends of chromosome arms. These comparisons
 585 were done once against the entire gene set (Figures S14, S15, and S17) and here using a
 586 permutation test with 1,000,000 draws of a random set of 410 genes where the red line
 587 indicates the observed value. (A) GC rich genes are clustered in the genome. The observed
 588 distance between each outlier gene and its nearest outlier gene neighbor is significantly shorter
 589 than those distances between a random group of genes (observed = 1.71Mbp, mean =
 590 2.89Mbp, n=1,000,000 permutations, $p < 0.000001$). (B) GC-rich genes occur closer to
 591 recombination hotspots than expected by chance (observed = 21.68Mbp, mean = 27.29Mbp, n
 592 = 1,000,000, $p < 0.00058$). (C) GC rich genes are found closer to the telomere end of
 593 chromosome arms than expected by chance (observed = 71.46%, mean = 49.78%,
 594 n=1,000,000, $p < 0.000001$). (D) GC-rich genes are clustered nearer telomere repeats
 595 (interstitial or otherwise) than expected by chance (observed = 11.79Mbp, mean = 15.06Mbp,
 596 n=1,000,000, $p < 0.000001$).

597

598 Figure 5. Distribution of recombination events in gerbil spermatocytes. (A) Immunolocalization of
 599 SYCP3 protein (grey) on meiotic chromosomes marks the trajectory of the synaptonemal
 600 complex along bivalents; trimethylation of histone H3 at lysine 9 (H3K9me3, blue) marks
 601 heterochromatin; CENT (red) stains centromeres; and MLH1 (green) marks the sites of
 602 crossovers. H3K9me3 is associated with the entirety of chromosome 13 (#13), a large intra-arm
 603 region of chromosome 5 (#5), and, to a lesser extent, the X and Y. The anti-CENT antibody
 604 (red) stains centromeres on all chromosomes but is not specifically associated with the large
 605 centromeric expansion of the long arm of chromosome 5. MLH1 foci can be located proximally,
 606 interstitially, or distally along bivalent 5 (central details, selected from three different
 607 spermatocytes), but they are never found within the centromere repeat expansion on this
 608 chromosome. Chromosome 13 shows either proximal or distal location of MLH1 foci (details on
 609 the right). (B) and (C) Graphs of MLH1 frequency against distance from the nearest telomere for
 610 bivalents 5 and 13, respectively. Each dot represents the location of the MLH1 focus along the
 611 synaptonemal complex on a single spermatocyte. The locations of centromeres and the
 612 chromosome 5 expansion are indicated as red and maroon boxes, respectively, on the
 613 schematic chromosomes below each graph. The graphs and drawings preserve the relative size
 614 of both chromosomes. For chromosome 5, most crossovers (over 80%) are located from the
 615 heterochromatic expansion towards the distal end. For chromosome 13, MLH1 foci are
 616 conspicuously accumulated towards the chromosomal ends, with an approximate 70:30
 617 distribution on the long and short arms respectively.

618

619 Figure 6. Chromosome 13 is unusual in terms of gene content and repetitive DNA density. (A)
 620 There is a strong relationship between chromosome length and gene number, but both
 621 chromosome 13 and the X have more genes than expected for their length. (B) When duplicate
 622 genes are removed, chromosome 13 and both sex chromosomes have far fewer genes than
 623 expected based on their length (error bars show the 95% confidence interval). (C) Chromosome
 624 13 is enriched for GC-rich genes. (D) Chromosome 13 has far higher repetitive DNA content
 625 than the other autosomes and is rivaled only by the Y. Panels E-M show a self-alignment of a

626 selection of “typical” chromosomes (E: Chr10; F: Chr16; G: Chr21), as well as three of the
627 longer scaffolds from the highly repetitive chromosome 13 (H, I, J) and the Y (K, L, M). Each
628 panel shows a 2Mbp section of chromosome and only alignments longer than 1,000 bases are
629 plotted. The primary alignments are clearly visible as diagonal lines at $y=x$. All alignments off of
630 the 1:1 line are repetitive sequence. The prevalence of repetitive sequence on chromosome 13
631 is much higher than other autosomes, and is most similar to the situation on the Y chromosome
632 (D). However, repeats on chromosome 13 (H, I, J) are much longer than those on the Y (K, L,
633 M), as expected based on their fundamentally different evolutionary history.

634

635 **References**

636

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